

1 **Gatad2a and Gatad2b connect the basal transcriptional machinery to Xist through selective control**
2 **of ILF2 and ILF3.**

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7 We used proteomic approach to identifying novel Xist interacting factors and combined this methodology
8 with study of Xist regulated mRNAs to precisely identify Xist transcriptional targets and interaction
9 partners. Here we identified two GATA family nuclear factors associated with Xist, Gatad2a and Gatad2b,
10 that exert selective control of the core Xist RNP binding partners ILF2 and ILF3. We conclude that these
11 GATA factors are necessary components of a basal transcriptional activation or elongation process in
12 which Xist is a regular interactant.

13 Citations

14 1. Mor, N., Rais, Y., Sheban, D., Peles, S., Aguilera-Castrejon, A., Zviran, A., Elinger, D., Viukov, S.,
15 Geula, S., Krupalnik, V. and Zerbib, M., 2018. Neutralizing Gatad2a-Chd4-Mbd3/NuRD complex facilitates
16 deterministic induction of naive pluripotency. Cell stem cell, 23(3), pp.412-425.